

A narrative overview of antimicrobial activity of metal nanoparticles

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Abstract: In recent years, the growing resistance of microorganisms to antibiotics has caused severe health issues. Novel uses of metallic compounds have been found by integrating current technologies such as nanotechnology and material science with the natural antibacterial activity of metals. Nanoparticles (NPs) are increasingly being used to target bacteria as an alternative to antibiotics. The use of nanotechnology in the treatment of bacterial infections might be extremely beneficial. Antibacterial coatings for implantable devices and medicinal materials to prevent infection and promote wound healing, antibiotic delivery systems to treat disease, bacterial detection systems to generate microbial diagnostics, and antibacterial vaccines to control bacterial infections are just some of the applications for NPs. According to the investigations, nanoparticles are a type of material that has been examined for their antibacterial characteristics. The current review focuses on recent research on the antimicrobial activity of metal nanoparticles, their synthesis, and their mechanisms of action. Antimicrobial mechanisms of Nanoparticles are poorly known, although oxidative stress induction, metal ion release, and non-oxidative processes are presently acknowledged. According to the research, the size of particles was the most important factor in determining the antimicrobial efficacy of metal nanoparticles. However, further research is needed to reduce the toxicity of nanoparticles so that they can be used as appropriate antibiotic and disinfection alternatives, particularly in biomedical applications.

Keywords: Nanoparticles, Nanotechnology, Antimicrobial, Biocides, Antibiotics

1. Introduction

Antibiotic resistance is a long-standing concern, and the "resistome" is a dynamic and growing issue. Overpopulation, increased worldwide movement, increased use of antibiotics in clinics and livestock production, selection pressure, inadequate sanitation, wildlife dispersal, and a poor sewage disposal system are all factors that contribute to the global resistome. Antibiotic therapy is one of the most used methods of infection control in modern medicine. Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a major worldwide hazard to the human, animal, and environmental health that is gaining traction. The development, spread, and persistence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacteria, sometimes known as "superbugs," is to blame (1). The expansion of research efforts in different science and technology sectors has substantially enhanced nanostructured materials (NMs) during the last few years. Nanomaterials are materials with at least one nanometer-scale dimension (1–100 nm) or whose fundamental unit in three-dimensional space is in this range. They've been hailed as a potential material for the development of nanomaterial-based biomedical technologies due to their size-dependent characteristics (2). Nanomaterials have unique physicochemical and biological properties that enable them to be used as promising materials in nanomedicine, allowing for the development of effective and novel biomedical modalities for a variety of applications, including medical diagnosis, gene therapy, drug delivery, cancer treatment, and so on. These can be found in electronic devices, cosmetics, military uses, photovoltaic cells, paints, catalysts, clean energy production, biocides, sanitizers, and a variety of other applications (as shown in Figure 1) (3).

Nanoparticles are synthesized by physical and chemical methods commercially. However, due to the modification of some stabilizing agents, high radiation, and high concentrated reductants, these procedures may

pose a risk. Therefore, the biological synthesis of NPs is another strategy that many researchers have employed. These eco-friendly approaches do not contain expensive and toxic chemicals (4). In these routes, NPs are fabricated by either cell extracts from microbial species or plant extracts as templates, which provides green synthetic approaches that effectively replace the use of expensive/toxic chemicals. The utilization of medicinal plants is the safest of these strategies. Hybrid techniques, which blend organic and inorganic substances, are another type of biological synthesis. The "green synthesis" of metallic nanoparticles is popular among other approaches due to its safe procedure. Several researchers have shown green biosynthesis of different metallic nanoparticles. Table 1 shows the summary of some nanoparticles that are produced by green synthesis procedures (5). NPs may readily penetrate biological molecules to be integrated into such systems due to their unique physicochemical features, such as large surface area, compact size, and excellent chemical reactivity. Generally, any materials or chemical compounds intended to kill bacteria locally or slow down their growth with the least toxic effects on the surrounding tissue are collectively referred to as antimicrobial agents (6). Antibacterial activities of NPs have been established against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria in particular. The powerful functions of several NPs (metals—Cu, Au, Ag, and Pt; and metal oxides—Ag₂O, SiO₂, TiO₂, CuO, CaO, ZnO, Fe₂O₃, and MgO) for their antibacterial activities against diverse microbes have been studied for successful integration of nanotechnology into medicines. These investigations indicated that the NPs function as potential microbial agents, inhibiting microbial development through a variety of bio-pathways, including the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), blockage of the electron transport chain, and antioxidant molecule depletion (through the alteration of enzymatic production of ROS). The mechanistic action mechanism of NPs has been

thoroughly characterized by several research groups. Moreover, numerous review publications have already highlighted the importance of nanoparticle syntheses, characterization, and bio-application (7,8). In this review, recent research on the antimicrobial activity of metal nanoparticles such as silver, gold, copper, carbon, zinc, etc., has been discussed. Furthermore, their mechanisms of action and synthesis have also been deliberated.

Figure 1: Few Major applications of Nanomaterial

2. Mode of action of nanoparticles as antimicrobial agents

Metal-based NPs, like antibiotics, can distinguish prokaryotic (bacterial) from eukaryotic (mammalian) cells by using the bacteria's metal transport mechanism and metalloproteins. Metal-based NPs, on the other hand, trigger bactericidal efficiency through numerous routes, unlike antibiotics (9). Figure 2 shows the mechanism of antimicrobial activity of nanoparticles.

2.1 Interactions with Phospholipid Bilayer

By attaching electrostatically to the bacterial cell wall and/or releasing metallic ions, metal-based NPs can impair cell membrane potential and integrity. Because

NPs have a positive charge and cellular components have a negative charge, they interact at the surface through electrostatic communication. These interactions harm bacterial proteins by disrupting the membrane and increasing oxidative stress. A large volume of water from the cytosol is discharged when the cell barrier is broken. Proton efflux pumps and electron transport in bacteria help cells compensate for this loss. However, the increased demand for these ions damages these transmembrane systems severely. Overall, this ion imbalance and membrane instability causes reduced respiration, energy transduction disruption, and cell death. The interaction of silver, gold, zinc oxide, magnesium oxide, and titanium oxide NPs have proven this effect. The ions generated by silver NPs interact particularly with sulfur-containing components within the cell membrane, preventing cell wall formation. (10,11).

2.2 Binding to Cytosolic Proteins

Metallic-based NPs induce an antibacterial response primarily through binding to cytosolic proteins such as enzymes and DNA. As a result of this interaction, respiratory and metabolic activities and ATP production are inhibited, resulting in decreased function. Silver, for example, attaches to enzymes in the respiratory chain and DNA, preventing them from replicating and dividing. Gold, on the other hand, interacts with DNA by causing the cell to upregulate genes. This leads to a loss of membrane integrity and reactive oxygen species (ROS) accumulation in the cell's cytoplasm (12).

2.3 Formation of Reactive Oxygen Species

The formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) or oxygen-free radicals, such as hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) or superoxide anions, is another way by which NPs kill bacteria. The NPs themselves cause the formation of ROS indirectly. ROS produce severe oxidative stress and damage to the cell's macromolecules, resulting in lipid peroxidation, protein modification, enzyme inhibition,

and RNA/DNA damage. Severe oxidative stress can potentially cause cell-lysis by forming holes or pits in the bacterial membrane. Silver has been shown to produce hydroxyl radicals (OH). Increased catalytic activity generates H_2O_2 from glucose oxidase in gold, zinc oxide, and magnesium oxide, demonstrating ROS generation. Titanium dioxide has evoked ROS production from both OH and H_2O_2 when exposed to light. When gallium was mistaken for iron, it caused the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) (13).

Figure 2: Mechanism of Antimicrobial activity of Nanoparticles

3. Nanoparticles showing antimicrobial activity against various pathogens

Several types of metal and metal oxide nanoparticles such as silver (Ag), silver oxide (Ag_2O), titanium dioxide (TiO_2), zinc oxide (ZnO), gold (Au), calcium oxide (CaO), silica (Si), and magnesium oxide (MgO), etc., have been known to show antimicrobial activity (14-17). Some of them are explained below. Table 2 highlights the antibacterial activity of metal-based nanoparticles, highlighting the bacterial strains that were evaluated, the mode of action, and the manufacturing processes that were utilized.

3.1. Silver Nanoparticles (AgNPs)

In recent years, silver NPs have shown significant advancements in various fields of sciences, medical, analytical sciences, material sciences, and health care fields. They have demonstrated excellent antibacterial capabilities against a variety of microorganisms. Nanostructured Ag materials have also been widely utilized as biomedical probes in the treatment of wounds, burns, and the control of a variety of infectious illnesses. Silver has been discovered to have a wide biocidal impact against a variety of bacteria species by disrupting enzyme activity and membrane function. Because silver ions may destabilize bacterial membranes and increase permeability, this inhibits the functioning of key proteins and respiratory enzymes, causing bacterial nucleic acid (RNA and DNA) replication to break down and the ion transport mechanism to be inhibited (5, 18).

Kim et al. synthesized Ag nanoparticles and used a particle characterizer and transmission electron microscopy analysis to determine their form and size. Ag nanoparticles were tested for antibacterial efficacy against yeast, *E. coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Muller Hinton agar plates were utilized in these experiments, and Ag nanoparticles of various concentrations were added to liquid systems. As a consequence, at low concentrations of Ag nanoparticles, yeast and *E. coli* were suppressed, but the growth-inhibitory effects on *S. aureus* were moderate. These findings show that Ag nanoparticles may be utilized as efficient growth inhibitors in a variety of bacteria, potentially making them useful in medical devices and antimicrobial control systems (19).

The production of silver nanoparticles employing *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* and *Bacillus subtilis*, using $AgNO_3$ as a precursor was described in a study. The production of nanoparticles with a typical diameter less than 140 nm was verified by EDX, SEM, and DLS studies. Face-centered cubic silver crystals were verified by XRD, with the greatest intensity peak at $2=38.12^\circ$, which corresponds to the (111) diffraction

planes. After 24 hours of incubation, antibacterial activity was shown against gram-negative bacteria such as *E. coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella*, and gram-positive bacteria like *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pyogenes*. In addition, *Candida albicans* was used to test the antifungal activity (20).

An acidophilic actinobacteria strain was utilized as a new reducing agent in a study to create nanostructure silver particles in a single step. The HGG16n isolate of *Streptacidiphilus durhamensis* was used to efficiently synthesize bioactive silver nanoparticles in a low-cost, environmentally friendly, and non-hazardous way. The prepared AgNPs showed exceptional physicochemical as well as biochemical properties. The well- and disc-diffusion techniques were used to assess antibacterial activity. The biosynthesized silver nanoparticles had a crystalline structure and were mainly spherical in form, with sizes ranging from 8 to 48 nm. Antimicrobial activity of silver nanoparticles against pathogenic bacteria was shown to be greatest against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Proteus mirabilis*, with *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Bacillus subtilis* following closely behind (21).

Several analytical methods, including a UV-Visible spectrophotometer, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction pattern analysis, and atomic force microscopy, were used to analyze biosynthesized silver nanoparticles. The antibacterial efficacy of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) against clinically relevant pathogenic pathogens was assessed. The combined effects of metal nanoparticles and antibiotics against clinical infections were also investigated. The enhanced antibacterial activity of antibiotics against clinically relevant infections in the presence of biologically produced AgNPs was observed. Against the test pathogens, erythromycin had the greatest boosting impact (22).

3.2. Gold Nanoparticles (AuNPs)

Unlike Ag, gold (Au) is an inert and highly stable metal that cannot be readily dissociated. Gold nanoparticles are new materials with properties unique from those of standard materials, and they have great promise for use in chemistry, physics, biology, and medicine. Due to their optical and electrical characteristics, which are highly dependent on their form and size, gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) have gotten a lot of interest. By changing the components and concentrations, AuNPs of various forms and sizes may be readily synthesized (23). Various groups studied the efficacy of the produced gold nanoparticle against certain human diseases. The gold nanoparticles were synthesized by treating a 1 mM gold chloride solution with leaf extracts of *Annona muricata*. UV-visible spectrophotometer, transmission electron microscope (TEM), and Fourier transformed infrared spectroscopy were used to analyze the produced gold nanoparticles (FTIR). The antibacterial and antifungal properties of the gold nanoparticles that were produced were also examined. TEM examination was used to assess the shape, size, and structural characteristics of produced gold nanoparticles, which revealed a spherical mono-dispersed structure with a particle size of about 25.5 nm. The -N-H, -C=C, and -C-N functional groups are responsible for the capping and stability of produced gold nanoparticles, as revealed by FTIR analyses at 3271.14, 2111.91, and 1637.82 cm^{-1} . As the gold nanoparticles concentration grows, the efficacy of the gold nanoparticle against the test pathogens increases. Inhibition zones of produced gold nanoparticles against test fungus and bacteria vary from 30 to 66 percent and 40 to 54 percent, respectively. With increasing gold nanoparticle concentration, the efficacy of the produced gold nanoparticle against specific fungus and bacteria rises. As a result of the antibacterial and antifungal tests, the produced gold nanoparticles were shown to have high antimicrobial activity (24).

3.3. Zinc and Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles (ZnNPs & ZnONPs)

Zinc oxide (ZnO) is an inorganic compound widely used in everyday applications. Research on ZnO as an antimicrobial agent started in the early 1950s. The major breakthrough in the use of ZnO as an antibacterial came in 1995 when Sawai and his colleagues discovered that MgO, CaO, and ZnO powders exhibited antimicrobial properties against certain bacteria strains. Zinc is a vital nutrient that plays a crucial role in mammals' growth, development, and well-being. For example, zinc oxide (ZnO) is safely acknowledged by the U.S. food and drug administration (21CFR182.8991) (25). The exact mechanism of action of ZnO nanoparticles is still unknown. However, the antimicrobial activity of these nanoparticles is attributed to several mechanisms, including the release of antimicrobial ions, interaction of nanoparticles with microorganisms, subsequently damaging the integrity of the bacterial cell, and the formation of ROS by the effect of light radiation (26).

In a study, Zinc oxide nanoparticles were synthesized using biological and chemical reducing agents. Nanoparticles produced using the two techniques were compared in terms of yield, nature, and antibacterial activity. Hot and cold Aloe vera leaf extract was utilized in the biological approach, while sodium hydroxide was used as a reducing agent in the chemical process. XRD and SEM were used to characterize nanoparticles made using the two techniques. The MIC values of gram-positive and gram-negative bacterial strains were determined using the agar well diffusion technique, with yields and MIC values indicating significant differences (27).

Meruvu et al., used a chemical technique to manufacture zinc oxide nanoparticles and used a scanning electron microscope and an X-ray diffractometer to analyze them. It was also tested for antibacterial efficacy against *Bacillus subtilis* and *Escherichia coli*. (28).

Synthesized Zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) were examined for antibacterial growth inhibition and mechanistic activity in research. All pathogenic microorganisms were treated with nanoparticles with a 20-25 nm diameter and concentrations of 0, 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 g/mL. According to microbiological analysis results, the ZnO NPs (size 20-25 nm) have demonstrated potential action against the bacteria and fungus examined (29).

3.4. Carbon Based Nanoparticles

It has been known that carbon-based nanoparticles exhibit high antimicrobial activity as well. Fullerenes, single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs), and graphene oxide (GO) nanoparticles were shown to have significant microbicidal capabilities in early investigations. These new allotropic types of carbon have been discovered in the last two decades, and, since then, they have been used in many fields of science (30). It was also shown that carbon nanomaterials' size and surface area are key characteristics influencing their antibacterial activity; that is, increasing the surface area of nanoparticles by lowering their size improved their activity for bacteria contact (31, 32). The antibacterial action of nanoparticles is largely determined by their composition, surface modification, inherent characteristics, and microbe type. It's been suggested that carbon-based nanomaterials damage bacterial membranes as a result of oxidative stress (33, 34).

Varghese et al., reported the synthesis of carbon nanoparticles (CNPs) from kitchen soot. Their characterization was done through UV/visible spectroscopy, SEM, and XRD, as well as their antibacterial activity, was examined. Gram-negative *Proteus refrigere* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, as well as Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus haemolyticus*, were used to assess the antibacterial activity of the isolated carbon nanoparticles (35).

Aloe vera extract was used to improve the antibacterial activity of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) made from silver nitrate (AgNO₃). It was done by putting AgNPs on an activated carbon nanoparticle (ACNPs) for 30 minutes in an aqueous colloidal media while using ultrasonic agitation (40 kHz, 2 50 watts). The antibacterial activity of synthesized AgNPs and AgNPs-immobilized ACNPs against *E. coli* was 57.58 percent and 63.64 percent, respectively (for *E. coli*); 61.25 percent and 93.49 percent, respectively (for *E. coli*) (for *S. aureus*). Furthermore, when the AgNPs-immobilized ACNPs material was coated on cotton and polyester textiles, the antibacterial activity of the materials altered, becoming 19.23% (cotton; *E. coli*), 31.73 percent (polyester; *E. coli*), 13.36% (cotton; *S. aureus*), and 21.15 percent (cotton; *S. aureus*) (polyester; *S. aureus*) (36).

3.5. Copper Nanoparticles

Among the other metal NPs, the recent interest in the CuNPs is propelled by the advances of these NPs as a cheap alternative for expensive metal NPs in the area of microelectronics applications and the possibility of exploring them as ultimate antimicrobial agents. The specific mechanism of CuNPs' antibacterial activity is still a question. Several mechanisms appear to be at play, including the release of Cu²⁺ ions, their penetration and disruption of the cell membrane and metabolic pathway by chelating cellular enzymes and DNA damage (37).

Copper (Cu) hydrosol with tiny nanoparticles (NPs) (5 nm) with a limited size distribution was created by a group. CuNPs were tested for antibacterial activity against Gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922), Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923), and *Candida albicans*, a fungus (ATCC 10259). After 2 hours of interaction with CuNPs, the microbial decrease was measured as a function of CuNPs concentration. An atomic force microscope was used to investigate the surface and morphological

changes of the strains exposed to Cu NPs on a cellular level (AFM) (37).

Kruck et al. synthesized metallic monodisperse copper nanoparticles in an aqueous SDS solution by reducing copper salt with hydrazine. The average particle size was around 50 nanometers. According to antimicrobial tests, copper nanoparticles demonstrated action equivalent to silver nanoparticles and certain medications against Gram-positive bacteria, conventional and clinical strains, including methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. They have antifungal efficacy against *Candida* species as well (38).

3.6. Iron Nanoparticles

The structural properties of the generated nanoparticles were studied using Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy, UV–VIS absorption, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM), and X-ray diffraction (XRD). The effect of laser fluence on the characteristics of these nanoparticles was studied. The antibacterial activities of iron oxide nanoparticles were investigated using *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Serratia marcescens*. The findings indicated a substantial inhibition of both bacterial strains. The manufacturing circumstances were shown to have a significant impact on the antibacterial activity of these nanoparticles. The generated magnetic nanoparticles were used to capture *S. aureus* germs fast under the influence of a magnetic field (39).

3.7. Other Nanoparticles

A group used a sol-gel method to synthesize metal-substituted cobalt ferrites [M_xCo(1-x)Fe₂O₄ (M = Zn, Cu, Mn; x = 0.0, 0.25, 0.5, and 0.75)]. X-ray diffraction, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, scanning electron microscopy, surface investigation using the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller technique, and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy were used to validate the ferrite structures.

Table 1: Various green-synthesized metallic nanoparticles from various plants' extracts

Nanoparticle	Plant employed for NPs synthesis	NPs size	Activity	References
Zinc oxide Nanoparticles (ZnO NPs)	Aqueous extract of <i>Lantana aculeata</i> Linn. leaf	12 ± 3 nm	Antifungal activity against plant fungal pathogens	(43)
	Leaves of <i>Pongamia pinnata</i>	100 nm	Antibacterial activity	(44)
Silver nanoparticles (Ag NPs)	<i>Diospyros lotus</i> fresh leaf extracts	27 nm	Photo catalytic activity (PCA)	(45)
	Pod extract of <i>Cola nitida</i>	--	Antibacterial and antioxidant activities	(49)
	Indian male fern (<i>Dryopteris cochleata</i>)	35 nm	Therapeutic properties	(46)
	Leaf extract of <i>Lantana camara</i>	86 nm	Antimicrobial activity	(47)
	<i>Moringa olifera</i> leaf extract	30-38 nm	Antimicrobial effect	(48)
Gold nanoparticles (AuNPs)	Extract of <i>Salvia officinalis</i> , <i>Lippia citriodora</i> , <i>Pelargonium graveolens</i> and <i>Punica granatum</i>	< 20 nm	--	(50)
	<i>Galaxaura elongata</i> (powder or extract)	3.85–77.13 nm	Antibacterial activity	(51)
Copper nanoparticles (CuNPs)	Citron juice (<i>Citrus medica</i> Linn.)	10–60 nm	Antimicrobial activity	(52)

Table 2: Summary of recently employed nanoparticles showing antimicrobial activity against various pathogens

Nanomaterial Employed	Source	Size	Microorganisms tested	Inhibition Concentration	Reference
Silver Nanoparticles (AgNPs)	<i>Streptacidiphilus durhamensis</i> HGG16n isolate	8 - 48 nm	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> , <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>Proteus mirabilis</i> , <i>E. coli</i> , <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> , <i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	-	(21)
	Chemical method	2-13 nm	<i>Escherichia coli</i> , and <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	-	(19)
	Chemical reduction method	20 nm	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i> , <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> and <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> .	-	(42)
	Biological method using cell supernatant of <i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i> and <i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	100 nm	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>E. coli</i> , <i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>Salmonella</i> , <i>S. pyogenes</i> and <i>C. albicans</i>	-	(20)
	Biological method by <i>Streptomyces</i> sp JAR1	-	<i>Salmonella enteric typhi</i> , <i>Bacillus cerus</i> , and <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> .	-	(22)
Zinc oxide Nanoparticles (ZnONPs)	Precipitation method	20-25 nm	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> and <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> , <i>Aspergillus</i> strain of <i>lavus</i> and <i>fumigatus</i> .	0, 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 µg/mL	(29)
	Chemical method	-	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> and <i>Escherichia coli</i>	-	(28)

	Using biological (Aloe vera extract) and chemical reducing agents (Sodium Hydroxide)	100 nm	<i>Bacillus subtilis, E.coli, Klebsiella pneumoniae, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, salmonella typhi, Staphylococcus aureus</i>	3-5mg/ml	(27)
Gold Nanoparticles (AuNPs)	Biological method by leaf extracts of <i>Annona muricata</i>	25.5 nm	<i>Aspergillus flaws, Candida albican, Fusarium oxysperium and Penicillium camemeri</i>	2 mg/l	(24)
Silver-zinc oxide nanoparticles (Ag—ZnO NPs)	Chemical method	-	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i> ATCC 29212, <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 6538 (Gram-positive bacteria), <i>Escherichia coli</i> ATCC 8739 (Gram-negative bacteria), <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> ATCC 27853 (Gram-negative bacteria) and <i>Candida albicans</i> ATCC 10231 (fungal strain).	1.875 mg/m L to 7.5 mg/mL.	(41)
Magnesium oxide nanoparticles	By biological method employing leaves extract of <i>Rhododendron arboreum</i>	-	<i>Escherichia coli, Spectrococcus mutans</i> and <i>Proteus vulgaris.</i>	-	(17)
Iron oxide Nanoparticles (Fe ₂ O ₃ NPs)	Pulsed laser ablation	50–110 nm	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> and Gram-negative; <i>Escherichia coli, Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> and <i>Serratia marcescens.</i>	-	(39)
Copper Nanoparticles	Chemical Method	5.3 nm	<i>E. coli, S. aureus, and C. albicans</i>	-	(37)

	Chemical reduction method	50 nm	Antibacterial activity against <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , antifungal activity against <i>Candida</i> species	-	(38)
Cobalt ferrite nanoparticles	Sol-gel method	1.84 nm	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> , <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> and <i>Candida albicans</i> .	-	(40)

These ferrites were tested for antimicrobial activity against a variety of harmful bacteria. After the metals were replaced, the structures retained cubic spinel phases. Substitution has a big impact on the microstructure and grain distribution. The particle size of the ferrites grew linearly when the annealing temperature was raised. The surface area of 52.56 m²/g, the average pore size of 1.84 nm, and the pore volume of 0.136 mL/g were measured in zinc cobalt ferrite nanoparticles (ZCFO). Against all microbes examined, all ferrites were antimicrobial. With inhibition zones of 13.0 mm against *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus* and 12.0 mm against *Candida albicans*, ZCFO proved to be the most effective. Gamma-irradiated ZCFO nanoparticles (150.0 kGy) have a higher antibacterial activity than non-irradiated particles (40).

Using silver nitrate, three types of anionic polyelectrolytes, and citric acid as reagents, a group, recently produced silver-zinc oxide nanoparticles (Ag ZnO NPs) chemically by deposition of Ag NPs on the surface of ZnO NPs. With the least inhibitory doses ranging from 1.875 mg/mL to 7.5 mg/mL, the synthesized Ag ZnO NPs showed antibacterial activity against all of the tested medically important microorganisms. The newly synthesized Ag ZnO NPs are active against planktonic and adhering bacteria, according to the study, and might be used to develop innovative antimicrobial methods for biotechnology and

medicinal applications (41).

4. Conclusion and Future Prospects

Numerous researches have been conducted to enhance antimicrobial methods due to rising microbe resistance to conventional disinfectants and medicines. In recent years, several important research in the realm of antimicrobial nanoparticles has been published. Metal nanoparticles might be a viable alternative to several antibacterial treatments. Antimicrobial nanoparticles might be useful for sterilizing medical equipment in the pharmaceutical and biomedical sectors. Chemical disinfectants, coating-based applications, and food preparation procedures might all benefit from these nanostructures. The antimicrobial properties of metal nanoparticles (particularly metal oxide nanoparticles) are impressive. Understanding nanotoxicity and its consequences is essential due to the promising development and widespread application of nanoparticles. Pharmaceutical sciences have been using nanoparticles for years to minimize medication toxicity and adverse effects; nonetheless, there are certain safety concerns concerning nanoparticles. The primary issues in using nanoparticles, according to studies, are neurological and respiratory impairment, cardiovascular difficulties, and other adverse consequences of nanoparticles. Several types of nanoparticles appear non-toxic, and some have been turned non-toxic with health benefits. One of these important health concerns might

be using nanoparticles' antibacterial ability to eliminate bacterial infections.

We think that the development of low-cost and simple inorganic antibacterial agents such as metal and metal oxide nanoparticles as an alternative to conventional antibiotics might be promising in the future for controlling various bacterial infections.

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6. Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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